

The Influence of Service Quality and Company Image on Customer Satisfaction and Word of Mouth

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to investigate the relationship among service quality, company image, customer satisfaction, and word of mouth. The population of this study is the parents of students in Avesiena Nature School Malang, East Java, Indonesia, which is 193 people. This study used saturated sample, it means the sample is the same number with the population. In order to examine the relationship both direct and indirect between service quality and company image on word of mouth, this study used path analysis. According to validity and reliability tests, the data that used in this study can be said valid and reliable. Results of this study show that service quality, company image, and customer satisfaction have a significant impact on word of mouth. Indirectly or through customer satisfaction, service quality and company image also have a significant effect.

Key words: Service Quality, Company Image, Customer Satisfaction, Word of Mouth

Introduction

The 21st century is marked by sharp competition in various fields of life, including in the world of education and shows an increasingly global trend. This condition requires every education service provider to focus more on meeting the needs and desires of students, namely students and users so that they are able to win the competition. To achieve this, various parties involved in school management are required to always improve the quality of graduates on an ongoing basis (continuous quality improvement). Given the quality of graduates has a significant influence on the ability of an educational institution to win the competition.

The importance of service quality as a determinant of organizational performance and a source of competitive advantage has become a key principle in service marketing. Schools as service organizations should use these principles as an effort to win the competition through various strategic considerations. The service factor must be used as the main strategy that allows an educational institution to be known for having certain characteristics that make it different from other educational institutions. Therefore, excellent service must be implemented and can be felt satisfactorily by students.

Service quality contributes significantly to the creation of differentiation, positioning and competitive strategy. The implication is that providing excellent service quality does not only lead to repeat buying, but is also able to become a positive reference and become a barrier against competitors. To implement satisfactory service, it requires synergy from all aspects of service so that it has implications for increasing customer loyalty. Creating customer value and customer satisfaction is at the heart of modern marketing thinking and practice. It is known that competitive advantage is positively correlated with the quality of human resources and is closely related to the role of education. This indicates that improving the quality of human resources should be the main focus in the national education system. Educational institutions have several customers, namely students, staff, teachers and alumni. Educational institutions are known as producers of educational services which are expected by the community to realize the quality of human resources through learning systems and processes in schools. The quality of education is a key factor in creating a national competitive advantage. Even though the quality of education is not visible, its impact can be seen in various fields and can be felt. An educational institution that is capable of producing quality graduates can be recognized, among others, by the presence of student satisfaction, an increase in the number of applicants (prospective students).

Marketing activity is a means for educational institutions (schools) to obtain prospective students according to the requirements. To achieve this goal, educational institutions (schools) must be able to produce quality graduates according to market needs through an effective academic service system, educational support facilities that adequate, non-academic services and teaching and learning processes that have an impact on student satisfaction.

Rashid and Jusoff (2009) stated that customer satisfaction has an important influence on corporate image to attract new customers through direct recommendations. In general, the choice of prospective students/student parents towards a school is influenced by their perceptions of the school. A school that has a good image will be chosen by prospective students/parents. Therefore, the image of the school affects the decisions of prospective students/parents when choosing a school. Building an image takes time, commitment and the right strategy. Pura (2005) states that if a company succeeds in creating a positive and strong image, the results will be felt in the long term let alone being able to maintain it consistently.

The quality of service in the context of schools has similarities with the service industry in general. This can be interpreted if a school is able to provide the best quality service to students, then their loyalty will be formed at that school. Furthermore, they will spread positive information and provide word of mouth recommendations to their closest people, relatives or friends to attend education at the school. Lymperopoulos and Chaniotakis (2008), stated that customer satisfaction can encourage customers to do positive word of mouth. Setyawati (2009), in her research stated that service quality had a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction, service quality had a significant effect on word of mouth, and patient satisfaction had a positive and significant effect on word of mouth. Praswati (2009) also states that service quality has a positive effect on word of mouth communication. Commitment has a positive effect on word of mouth communication. The strength of the relationship has a positive effect on word of mouth communication. Word of mouth communication has a positive effect on intention to use services again.

This study aims to investigate the influence of service quality and company image on customer satisfaction and word of mouth in the Avesiena Nature School Malang, East Java, Indonesia. Avesiena Nature School Malang is one of the educational institutions in Indonesia which is based on Islamic education that adheres to Islamic faith and piety. As an educational institution in Indonesia, attention to the quality of educational services is absolutely necessary. Efforts to improve the quality of educational services, including services in the academic and non-academic activities must always be carried out so that students get optimal satisfaction. Avesiena Nature School Malang has several advantages. First, this school is based on nature, meaning that students are introduced to nature, so that it is hoped that students will become human beings who can synergize with nature. Second, Avesiena Nature School Malang as early as possible students are introduced to religion, in this case Islam. So that students are expected to do everything based on religious values.

Avesiena Nature School Malang realizes that word of mouth is an effective marketing communication medium as a means of promotion to get prospective students. In this regard, in an effort to improve the image of Avesiena Nature School Malang as an institution that produces quality and professional human resources, the quality of service to students needs to receive more serious attention.

Literature Review

Service Quality

The quality of service in the education sector, especially in schools is a fundamental aspect of excellent education quality. Spooren et al. (2007) provide a point of view that organizational harmony, intellectual ability of teaching staff, professional development, and transparent evaluation of students, training and feedback are very important elements in students' mental development. Students will be more motivated if the school provides reliable facilities.

More specifically, the dimensions of service quality in schools, as stated by Kotler and Fox (1995:414), there are six main dimensions in the quality of services in schools, namely: Quality of instruction, Academic advising, Library resource, extracurricular activity, Opportunity to talk with faculty members, and Job placement service. Several studies investigated service quality in education institution (Herman, 2022; Smith & Ennew, 2001; Twum & Peprah, 2020). Using 81 students of Public Senior Higher School (SMA Negeri 3) in Teluk Lecah, Herman (2022) found that student happiness is positively and significantly impacted by the service quality. The outcome of the test of determination revealed that (R^2) is 0.849. This indicates that the service quality variable has an 84.9% impact on student satisfaction. The remaining 15.1% is affected by factors that were not looked at.

Smith & Ennew (2001) used data from a public sector context to further understanding of the effects of service quality. Due to the characteristics of the pertinent behavioral consequences, the chosen setting, Higher Education, is particularly intriguing. Because most higher education consumers only make one purchase, the outcomes that are the subject of considerable research attention—namely, retention, loyalty, profitability, etc.—are less relevant to them. The results of this restudy, which specifically emphasizes both the functional and technical components of service quality, reveal that the functional aspects are more important, even though the technical (outcome) quality has a significant effect on recommendation readiness. It's interesting to note that while end is more significant than method, the academic aspects of process have a greater influence than non-academic ones.

The primary goal of Twum & Peprah (2020) is to gauge how satisfied students are with the services offered by Valley View University's School of Business. The SERVQUAL Model, which has five service quality dimensions—tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, empathy, and assurance—was used to perform a cross-sectional adopted questionnaire survey with 100 students. The mean, standard deviation, and regression findings were calculated using the data analysis features of the SPSS program. The study's findings demonstrated that the School of Business's service quality and its characteristics of certainty, tangibles, and responsiveness were very satisfied, while empathy was only moderately so. Showed that the students had high expectations for the services the School of Business provided. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that the service quality aspects of assurance, tangible, responsiveness, reliability, and empathy may account for 100% of customer happiness. The report makes the recommendation that the School of Business attend to students' needs by giving them individualized attention to address their particular issues.

Company Image

In the world of marketing, the formation of a positive corporate image will greatly assist the company in its marketing activities, because in conditions of very tight competition, every company will try to place itself as well as possible in the eyes of its consumers so that it can be trusted to meet their needs. One strategy is to form a positive image as a variable that can influence consumers in the decision-making process. The higher the commitment of all components of the company to provide satisfactory service to customers, the better the customer's perception of service, and this also makes the company's image better.

Image is a role that is centered on customer perceptions of service quality or service quality. Image is important for a company or other organization. Therefore it is very important to manage the image in an appropriate manner. Image is an intangible asset or goodwill of a company that has a positive effect on the market's valuation of the company. Andreassen et al. (1998) in his research on consumer orientation suggests that image is an important factor that is interrelated with satisfaction and loyalty. Eva (2007) also explained that customer satisfaction has a significant effect on corporate image. Miles and Covin (2000) argue that corporate image is the view or perception of the company by people, both inside and outside the company.

Word of Mouth

Word of Mouth Communication, basically is a message about a company's products or services, or about the company itself, in the form of comments about product performance, friendliness, honesty, speed of service and other things that are felt and experienced by someone conveyed to someone else. The message conveyed can be in the form of a message that is positive or negative, depending on what is felt by the sender of the message for the services he consumes. According to the Word of Mouth Marketing Association (WOMMA), word of mouth is a marketing effort that triggers consumers to talk about, promote, recommend and sell products or brands to customers and other potential consumers.

Word of mouth behavior can be related to consumer satisfaction and dissatisfaction with previous consumption experiences (Blodget, 1993; Brown & Beltramini, 1989). Harisson & Walker in Brown et al. (1993) stated that word of mouth is an informal communication between a non-commercial speaker and a person who receives information about a brand, product, company or service. Word of mouth can be interpreted as a communication activity in marketing which indicates several possibilities that customers will tell others about their experiences in the process of purchasing a product or service. The customer experience can be positive or negative.

Word of mouth within certain limits affects the information gathering stage before the transaction process. Word of mouth has an influence on the awareness or product introduction stage and can have an impact on the consumer's final decision. (Mitchel, 2005:3). Word of mouth originates from a form that arises naturally

and is not designed by companies and marketers. Recently word of mouth is intended to replace conventional marketing communication programs such as advertisements which are increasingly losing credibility.

Word of mouth has such an important influence. Word of mouth becomes a strength because humans are social creatures, like to talk to each other about good things and bad things. (Jerram, 2003). According to Kartajaya (2007: 183), word of mouth is the most effective communication medium. Word of mouth recommendations are one of the important factors that influence a person's decision to buy a product/service. This is because in the service business it is difficult to know the quality factors both before and after purchase, where the characteristics of services are abstract in nature. Gremier (1994).

Customer Satisfaction

Lovelock and Wirtz (2007: 102) define satisfaction as an emotional state, a post-purchase reaction in the form of anger, dissatisfaction, aggravation, neutrality, joy, or pleasure. Bai and Chiao (2001) state that customer satisfaction is a mediator for all perceived service quality. Besides that, customer satisfaction is seen as the best indicator for the future. Kotler and Keller (2009:179), formulate 4 (four) methods for measuring customer satisfaction, which consist of: complaint and suggestion system, regular customer satisfaction surveys, ghost shopping, and lost customer analysis.

In the context education institution, Students will be more satisfied and motivated to complete their studies if the institution provides an academic environment that supports and motivates students to achieve success in developing their academic field. Students will be more motivated, loyal and perform well if the institution where they study provides adequate academic facilities with teaching staff who provide good teaching and skills training. Teacher performance inside and outside the classroom is very significant in driving student motivation and satisfaction.

Research Framework

Based on the theoretical review, the research framework of this study can be describe in the figure 1 below.

Figure 1
Research Framework

Figure 1 above shows that this research was to determine the effect of service quality (X1) and company image (X2) on word of mouth (Y) with customer satisfaction as an intervening variable. Based on the research framework, the hypothesis of this study are:

- H1: There is an influence of the service quality on the customer satisfaction of parents of students in the Avesiena Nature School Malang.
- H2: There is an influence of the company image on the customer satisfaction of parents of students in the Avesiena Nature School Malang.
- H3: There is an influence of the service quality on positive word of mouth of parents of students in the Avesiena Nature School Malang.
- H4: There is an influence of the company image on positive word of mouth of parents of students in the Avesiena Nature School Malang.
- H5: There is an influence of the customer satisfaction on positive word of mouth of parents of students in the Avesiena Nature School Malang.
- H6: There is an influence of the service quality on positive word of mouth with customer satisfaction as intervening variable of parents of students in the Avesiena Nature School Malang.
- H7: There is an influence of the company image on positive word of mouth with customer satisfaction as intervening variable of parents of students in the Avesiena Nature School Malang.

Research Method

This research is classified as explanatory research, namely the research design of hypothesis testing and causality. Technically the data analysis used is grouped into two, namely descriptive analysis and inferential statistical analysis, which in this study used path analysis (path analysis) using the SPSS program. The population in this study is 193 people / parents of students at the Avesiena Nature School in Malang. Starting from the playgroup level to the Elementary School level. The sampling method used in this study is the saturated sample method. Saturated sample method is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples.

This study has four variables. Those variables are service quality, company image, customer satisfaction, and word of mouth. Service quality is measured by tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Company image in this study was measured by reputation in society, ability to produce good graduates, and the fame of Avesiena Nature School Malang in the community. Customer satisfaction as intervening variable is measured by respondents' perception toward the indicators. Those indicators are: first, the ability of Avesiena Nature School Malang to provide services in accordance with the expectations of students' parents. Second is to evaluate of the Avesiena Nature School Malang. Third is to assess the decision to choose the Avesiena Nature School Malang, and the fourth is respondents' satisfaction with the service provided by Avesiena Nature School Malang. The dependent variable word of mouth is measured by respondents' perceptions of the following indicators: 1) Willingness to share positive things about the Avesiena Nature School Malang to others; 2) Willingness to recommend to others who need information about Avesiena Nature School Malang; and 3) Willingness to invite other people to send their children to Avesiena Nature School Malang. Data analysis that used in this study are validity and reliability tests, classical assumptions (normality, heteroscedasticity, linearity), and inferential statistics.

Results and Discussions

Respondents in this study were parents of students at Avesiena Nature School Malang. Based on the results of a questionnaire distributed to all parents of students at Avesiena Nature School Malang, totaling 193 people, the researcher obtained an overview of the respondents based on gender and age. Based on gender, there is 73 people or 38% are male and 120 people or 62% are female. It can be concluded that the highest number of respondents in this study were female. Frequency distribution of respondents based on age classified into 4 levels, namely 26-30 years, 50 people (26%), ages 31-40 years, 50 people (26%), aged 41-50 years 30 people (17%), and over 50 years 60 people (31%).

Classical assumptions that used in this study are normality, heteroscedasticity, and linearity tests. Normality test used Kolmogorov-Smirnov test using the p-value, where the p-value is greater than alpha indicating that the residual model follows a normal distribution. Result of normality test can be seen in the table 1 below.

Table 1 : Normality test

	Z - count	P Value	Description
Customer satisfaction (Y1) Service quality (X1) Company image (X2)	0.657	0.781	Normal
Word of Mouth (Y2) Service quality (X1) Company image (X2) Customer satisfaction (Y1)	0.934	0.347	Normal

Source: SPSS results

Based on table 1 above, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results were obtained with a Z count of 0.657 and a p-value of 0.781. This shows that the p-value (0.781) is greater than alpha (0.050) so that the model follows a normal distribution. The influence of Service Quality (X1), Company Image (X2), and Customer Satisfaction (Y1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) obtained the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z test results of 0.934 with a p-value of 0.347. This shows that the p-value (0.347) is greater than alpha (0.050) so that the model follows a normal distribution.

In this study, a heteroscedasticity test was carried out using the graphical method. To find out whether there is heteroscedasticity between independent variables, it can be seen from the plot graph between the

predicted value of the dependent variable (ZPRED) and its residual (SRESID). The result of heteroscedasticity test can be seen in the figure 1 below.

Figure 1 : Result of Heteroscedasticity Scatter Plot ZPRED* SRESID

The results of the analysis in Figure 1 show that the plot points between ZPRED and SRESID are randomly distributed and do not form a specific pattern. This shows that there is no indication of heteroscedasticity in equations 1 to 2 tested so that this assumption is fulfilled. The method used to test linearity is the curve estimation test. The influence of the two variables is said to be linear if the significance value of the test is smaller than the alpha used.

Table 2 : Linearity test (Curve Fit)

	F Count	P Value	Description
Customer satisfaction (Y1)			
Service quality (X1)	653,090	0,000	Linier
Company image (X2)	415,236	0,000	Linier
WOM (Y2)			
Company image (X2)	131,191	0,000	Linier
Customer satisfaction (Y1)	151,151	0,000	Linier

Source: SPSS results

Testing the assumptions of linearity in table 2 was carried out using the Curve Fit method by looking at the shape of the influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The test results show that the significance value for each effect is smaller than alpha 5%, so it can be concluded that the linearity assumption is met.

Path analysis is used to examine the effect of equation 1 between Service Quality (X1) and Company Image (X2) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1), and the effect of equation 2 between Service Quality (X1), Corporate Image (X2), and Customer Satisfaction (Y1) against Word Of Mouth (Y2).

Figure 2 : Path Chart

Path Equation 1

Path equation 1 formed on the effect of the equation between Service Quality (X1) and Company Image (X2) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is as follows.

$$Y1 = 0,620X1 + 0,313X2 + e1$$

The magnitude of the path coefficient on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) by Service Quality (X1) is 0.620 and Company Image (X2) is 0.313. The biggest influence on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) of this variable is Service Quality (X1) which is indicated by the largest path coefficient compared to other variables. The coefficient of determination (R²) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) by Service Quality (X1) and Company Image (X2) is 80.4% which means that 80.4% of the Customer Satisfaction factor (Y1) is influenced by the Service Quality factor (X1) and Company Image (X2) and the remaining 19.6% of the Customer Satisfaction factor (Y1) is influenced by factors other than these factors. The effect of error in equation 1 is obtained by

$$e1 = \sqrt{1 - 0.804} = 0.443$$

Path Equation 2

The path equation 2 formed in the influence of the equation between Service Quality (X1), Company Image (X2), and Customer Satisfaction (Y1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) are as follows.

$$Y2 = 0,241X1 + 0,201X2 + 0,286 Y1 + e2$$

The magnitude of the path coefficient to Word Of Mouth (Y2) by Service Quality (X1) is 0.241, Company Image (X2) is 0.201, and Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is 0.286. The biggest influence on Word Of Mouth (Y2) of this variable is Customer Satisfaction (Y1) which is indicated by the largest path coefficient compared to other variables. The coefficient of determination (R²) on Word Of Mouth (Y2) by Service Quality (X1), Company Image (X2), and Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is 47.8%, which means that 47.8% is the Word Of Mouth factor (Y2) is influenced by factors of Service Quality (X1), Corporate Image (X2), and Customer Satisfaction (Y1) and the remaining 52.2% Word Of Mouth factor (Y2) is influenced by factors other than these factors. The effect of the error in equation 2 is found to be $e2 = \sqrt{1 - 0.478} = 0.722$.

The total coefficient of determination explains how much the path model is formed in explaining the data used in the research. The value of the coefficient of determination ranges from 0.0% to 100%.

$$R^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.804) \times (1 - 0.478) = 0.898$$

The total determination coefficient obtained based on the results of the path model calculation above is 0.898 which indicates that the path model used can explain 89.8% of the data used in the study.

Hypothesis testing is conducted to test the initial hypothesis set out in the study. The comparison used is using the p-value, where the p-value is smaller than alpha indicating that the research hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3

Decomposition of Causality Effect Coefficients Between Variables

Effect	Direct	Indirect	Total
X1 → Y1	0.620		0.620
X1 → Y2	0.241	0.177	0.418
X2 → Y1	0.313		0.313

X2 → Y2	0.201	0.090	0.291
Y1 → Y2	0.286		0.286

Source: SPSS results

Below the discussion based on the results in the table 3 above.

Direct effect of service quality (X1) on customer satisfaction (Y1)

The initial hypothesis (H1) states that there is a significant direct effect between Service Quality (X1) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1). The results of the analysis of the direct effect of Service Quality (X1) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) obtained a p-value of 0.000. This value is smaller than alpha 5% indicating that there is a significant influence between Service Quality (X1) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1).

Table 4 : Direct effect of service quality (X1) on customer satisfaction (Y1)

Effect	Path Coefficient	Std. Error	t-count	p-value
X1-->Y1	0.620	0.037	10.760	0.000

Source: SPSS result

Based on table 4 above, the coefficient value of the direct effect of Service Quality (X1) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is 0.620 and has a positive and significant sign indicating that the form of influence of Service Quality (X1) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is directly proportional (positive) and significant which means that increasing the Service Quality factor (X1) will have a significant impact on increasing the Customer Satisfaction factor (Y1).

If seen from the results of the analysis which states that when the Avesiena Nature School Malang improves service quality, customers will respond positively by stating their satisfaction with the services provided. Service improvement activities by Avesiena Nature School Malang are in accordance with the opinion (Kotler, 1997) that improving service quality must start from customer needs and will shape customer perceptions. The increase in the quality of services provided by the Avesiena Nature School Malang indicates that Avesiena Nature School Malang response to student demands for service quality is very fast, so that users respond positively with positive perceptions.

An indicator of improving the service quality of the Avesiena Nature School Malang to its users when viewed from Lehtinen's perception in Ghobadian, et al. (1994) is the construction of a new building and its equipment to support the learning and teaching process at the Avesiena Nature School in Malang. In addition, the disclosure of information submitted education providers, in this case the Avesiena Nature School Malang, to users can be conveyed well.

The direct effect of company image (X2) on customer satisfaction (Y1)

Hypothesis 2 (H2) states that there is a significant direct effect between Company Image (X2) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1). The results of the analysis of the direct effect of Company Image (X2) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) obtained a p-value of 0.000. This value is smaller than the alpha of 5% indicating that there is a significant influence between Company Image (X2) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1).

Table 5 : Direct effect of company image (X2) on customer satisfaction (Y1)

Effect	Path Coefficient	Std. Error	t-count	Pvalue
X2 -->Y1	0.313	0.067	5.442	0.000

Source: SPSS result

Based on table 5 above, the coefficient value of the direct influence of Corporate Image (X2) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is 0.313 and has a positive and significant sign indicating that the influence of Corporate Image (X2) on Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is directly proportional (positive) and significant means that an increase in the Corporate Image factor (X2) will have a significant impact on increasing the Customer Satisfaction factor (Y1).

The results of the analysis show that service users are satisfied with the educational services at Avesiena Nature School Malang, so they have a good image. According to Alma (2005), image is an impression obtained in accordance with one's knowledge and experience about something. Quality improvement is able

to increase user satisfaction, so that simultaneously service quality is able to create user satisfaction and image for the community.

The image of Avesiena Nature School Malang that has been formed both in the eyes of users and the public will have an impact on good trust, so that when there is an increase in the price that must be paid by users of the services provided by Avesiena Nature School Malang, this will be responded positively. As revealed by Aydin and Zer (2005) who stated that when an image has been well formed and will bring trust from users, the company's policy of increasing prices will receive a positive response because the company has built trust and instilled loyalty to these consumers.

Direct effect of service quality (X1) on word of mouth (Y2)

Hypothesis 3 (H3) states that there is a significant direct effect between Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2). The results of the analysis of the direct effect of Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) obtained a p-value of 0.045. This value is smaller than alpha 5% indicating that there is a significant influence between Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2).

Table 6 : Direct effect of service quality (X1) on word of mouth (Y2)

Effect	Path Coefficient	Std. Error	t-count	Pvalue
X1 -->Y2	0.241	0.046	2.014	0.045

Source: SPSS result

Based on table 6 above, the coefficient value of the direct effect of Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) is 0.241 and is positive and significant indicating that the form of influence of Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) is directly proportional (positive) and significant which means that an increase in the Service Quality factor (X1) will have a significant impact on increasing the Word of Mouth factor (Y2).

The results of the analysis state that there is a significant direct effect between Service Quality on Word of Mouth. The quality of service provided by Avesiena Nature School Malang is able to provide more value to students' parents. Complete supporting facilities such as libraries, canteens, meeting halls, and places of worship really add value to Avesiena Nature School Malang to meet students' needs. According to Supranto (2006), one of the factors that determine the quality of school services or other institutions is the ability to provide quality services for service users or customers.

Direct effect of company image (X2) on word of mouth (Y2)

Hypothesis 4 (H 4) states that there is a significant direct effect between Company Image (X2) on Word of Mouth (Y2). The results of the analysis of the direct influence of company image (X2) on word of mouth (Y2) obtained a p-value of 0.049. This value is less than 5% alpha indicating that there is a significant influence between Company Image (X2) on Word of Mouth (Y2).

Table 7 : Direct effect of company image (X2) on word of mouth (Y2)

Effect	Path Coefficient	Std. Error	t-count	Pvalue
X2-->Y2	0.201	0.071	1.985	0.049

Source: SPSS result

Based on table 7 above, the coefficient value of the direct influence of Corporate Image (X2) on Word Of Mouth (Y2) is 0.201 and has a positive and significant sign indicating that the form of influence of Corporate Image (X2) on Word Of Mouth (Y2) is directly proportional (positive) and significant which means that increasing the Corporate Image factor (X2) will have a significant impact on increasing the Word of Mouth factor (Y2).

The results of the analysis state that there is a significant direct effect between corporate image and word of mouth. Strong corporate image has an impact on positive values in the eyes of students' parents being able to maintain the company's image, with this achievement parents feel confident that their children are studying at the Avesiena Nature School Malang. convey these advantages and recommend to the public to study at the Avesiena Nature School Malang. Corporate image is very helpful in the process of sustaining an institution. Image plays a central role for companies that want to win in competition with other companies (Jasfar, 2005).

Direct effect of customer satisfaction (Y1) on word of mouth (Y2)

Hypothesis 5 (H5) states that there is a significant direct effect between Customer Satisfaction (Y1) and Word Of Mouth (Y2). The results of the analysis of the direct effect of Customer Satisfaction (Y1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) obtained a p-value of 0.017. This value is less than alpha 5% indicates that there is a significant influence between Customer Satisfaction (Y1) on Word of Mouth (Y2).

Table 8 : Direct effect of customer satisfaction (Y1) on word of mouth (Y2)

Effect	Path Coefficient	Std. Error	t-count	Pvalue
Y1-->Y2	0.286	0.071	2.408	0.017

Source: SPSS result

Based on table 8 above, the coefficient value of the direct effect of Customer Satisfaction (Y1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) is 0.286 and is positive and significant indicating that the form of influence of Customer Satisfaction (Y1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) is directly proportional (positive) and significant which means that an increase in the Customer Satisfaction factor (Y1) will have a significant impact on increasing the Word of Mouth factor (Y2).

The results of the analysis show that there is a significant direct effect between customer satisfaction and word of mouth, Avesiena Nature School Malang provides a sense of satisfaction with the 5-day learning carried out intensively in the teaching and learning process that is applied.

Indirect effect of service quality (X1) on word of mouth (Y2) through customer satisfaction (Y1)

Hypothesis 6 (H6) states that there is a significant indirect effect between Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1). The results of the analysis of the indirect effect of Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1) obtained a p-value of 0.000. This value is smaller than alpha 5% indicating that there is a significant influence between Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1).

Table 9 : Indirect effect of service quality (X1) on word of mouth (Y2)

Effect	Path Coefficient	Std. Error	t-count	P-value
X1 -->Y1-->Y2	0.177	0.045	3.910	0.000

Source: SPSS result

Based on table 9 above, the coefficient value of the indirect effect of Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is 0.177 and has a positive and significant sign indicating that the form of influence of Service Quality (X1) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is directly proportional (positive) and significant, which means that an increase in the Service Quality factor (X1) will have a significant impact on increasing the Word of Mouth factor (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1).

The results of the analysis state that there is a significant indirect effect between corporate image and word of mouth through customer satisfaction. This happened because the seriousness of the Avesiena Nature School Malang in developing the company's image by increasing the quality of service, was welcomed by the parents of the students, this good reception was manifested through Word of Mouth that the parents of the students would recommend the community to study at the Avesiena Nature School Malang.

Indirect effect of company image (X2) on word of mouth (Y2) through customer satisfaction (Y1)

The hypothesis states that there is a significant indirect effect between Company Image (X2) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1). The results of the analysis of the indirect effect of Company Image (X2) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1) obtained a p-value of 0.003. This value is smaller than alpha 5% shows that there is a significant influence between Corporate Image (X2) on Word Of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1).

Table 10 : Indirect effect of company image (X2) on word of mouth (Y2)

Effect	Path Coefficient	Std. Error	t-count	P-Value
X2-->Y1-->Y2	0.090	0.030	3.011	0.003

Source: SPSS result

Based on table 10 above, the coefficient value of the indirect effect of Company Image (X2) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is 0.090 and has a positive and significant sign indicating that the influence of Company Image (X2) on Word of Mouth (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1) is directly proportional (positive) and significant, which means that an increase in the Company Image factor (X2) will have a significant impact on increasing the Word of Mouth factor (Y2) through Customer Satisfaction (Y1).

The results of the analysis state that there is a significant indirect effect between company image and word of mouth through customer satisfaction. In line with the results of research by Loanis and Constantine (2009), that new mothers are more satisfied, and they have more will to say positive things (positive WOM). The existence of a good corporate image in the eyes of the community will result in satisfaction for parents of students. The satisfaction of the students' parents is manifested by the students' parents by assessing the Avesiena Nature School Malang through Word of Mouth, and the parents of the students will said positive things about the Avesiena Malang Nature School to the wider community.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that service quality and corporate image are proven to affect the level of satisfaction of parents of students at Avesiena Nature School Malang. The better the quality of service and corporate image, the satisfaction of parents of students will also increase. In addition, both service quality, corporate image and the level of satisfaction of parents of students are proven to influence Word of Mouth. The higher the level of satisfaction felt by parents of students, the Word of Mouth factor will also increase.

For the school, it is expected to further improve the quality of service, especially tangible factors, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. At the same time maintaining and improving the company's image including company reputation, physical image, and public relations in order to get a good image among parents of students. It is suggested for further researchers to enrich the research domain by adding variables that have not been tested in this study, for example regarding customer loyalty. Besides that, it also expands the research location so that it can be proven in other locations.

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